

DESIGN AND ANALYSIS OF ADHESIVELY BONDED THICK COMPOSITE PATCH REPAIR OF CORROSION GRIND OUT AND CRACKS ON 2024 T3 CLAD ALUMINUM AIRCRAFT STRUCTURES

A. Chukwujekwu Okafor and Hari Bhogapurapu
Structural Health Monitoring and NDE Laboratory
Department of Mechanical and Aerospace Engineering
University of Missouri-Rolla
1870 Miner Circle, Rolla MO 65409-0050, USA*

SUMMARY: Many military and commercial aging aircrafts are flying beyond their design life may experience severe crack and corrosion damage, and thus lead to catastrophic failures. In this paper, the design, fabrication and analysis of adhesively bonded thick composite patch repair of circular corrosion grind-out and a crack propagating on the periphery of the grind-out on thick 2024 T3 clad aluminum aircraft panel is presented. Thick composite patch configurations of 7-25 plies were designed separately for crack and corrosion grind-out using CRAS. Using the principles of superimposition a single patch was designed to repair both the crack and corrosion grind-out. Finite element analysis (FEA) was performed on the test specimen subjected to uni-axial tensile loading. Stress distribution and displacements were obtained and analyzed. Dog-bone shaped tensile test panels were fabricated with damage and repaired with boron/epoxy patch of 11 plies. The patched and un-patched panels were subjected to tensile tests. The experimental and the FEA results show that the maximum skin stress decreases significantly and shifted away from damaged area after the application of composite patch. The load carrying capacity of patched specimen significantly increased over that for un-patched specimen.

Keywords: Crack and Corrosion grind-out, Thick composite patch repair, Aging aircraft structure, Superimposition, Stress distribution, Finite element analysis.

1. INTRODUCTION

Aging aircraft problem is one of the serious challenges to commercial and military aircraft operators. The high acquisition costs associated with the purchase of modern aircrafts, coupled with the increased budget cuts in the acquisition of new aircraft fleets have resulted in the utilization of aircrafts beyond their original design life. Corrosion and fatigue are the major factors that contribute to the aging of aircraft. During its service life, an aircraft is subjected to severe structural and aerodynamic loads which may result from repeated landings and take-off, fatigue, ground handling, bird strikes and environmental degradation such as stress corrosion, which cause damage or weakening of structure. A repair or reinforcement of the structure to restore the structural efficiency and thus assure the continued airworthiness of the aircraft has become an important issue in recent years. Advanced composite materials have many advantages like high specific strength and stiffness, lightweight, resistance to corrosion, directional dependence of the material properties, ability to be formed to conform complex shapes and contours and to meet variable stiffness requirement.

*Corresponding Author, Tel: 1-(573) 341-4695, Email: okafor@umr.edu (A.C.Okafor)

The technique of repairing cracked metallic aircraft structures using high strength advanced composite materials is commonly known as "crack patching". The composite reinforcement, also known as a patch, can be attached to the damaged or weakened structure either by mechanical fastener or adhesive bonding. The use of adhesively bonded composite patches [1] has several advantages over mechanically fastened repair methods, which include reduced installation cost, increased strength and fatigue life, reduced repair down time, elimination of unnecessary fastener holes in an already weakened structure and stress concentrations at fasteners, corrosion resistance, high stiffness and lightweight [1].

This paper presents the design, finite element modeling and analysis technique for single sided thick composite patch repair of corrosion grind-outs and crack on the periphery of 2024-T3 aluminum aircraft panels [2,3,4]. The objectives of this research are 1) to develop a procedure for designing thick composite patch (the number of plies more than 10, preferably greater than 20) for the repair of circular corrosion grind-out and crack at the periphery of the circular grind-out, (2) to study the complicated stress distribution on the damaged aluminum specimen repaired with symmetric octagonal patch under axial tensile fatigue loading, 3) to experimentally verify the durability of patched and unpatched panels to validate the FEA results.

2. DESIGN OF PATCH

A combination of shear, axial, normal, peel and cleavage loading make up the primary loads acting on adhesive bonds. A good repair must be effective in minimizing these effects. Patch design must address the following issues.

2.1 Patch Thickness

It has been found that the patch is most effective when the patch stiffness ($E_p t_p$) is equal to skin (aluminum panel) stiffness ($E_s t_s$). Where E_p and E_s are the modulus of elasticity of patch material, and skin material respectively; t_p and t_s are the thickness of composite patch and skin (aluminum) material. The ratio of patch stiffness to skin stiffness is called the Stiffness Ratio (SR) and has an ideal value of 1. The recommended stiffness ratio (SR) ranges from 1.0 to 1.6.

2.2 Adhesive

Adhesive properties influence the strength of the joint since the load is transferred from the skin to patch via the adhesive. The thickness of adhesive layer is an important issue in designing a patch. Thin adhesive layers are shown to perform better than thick layers because with increase in adhesive thickness the patch gets softer. But thickness provides good durability to the entire patch, as thick patch adhesive layer attracts lesser strains. Stiffer adhesives perform better but if the adhesive is very stiff, there is a danger for the patch reaching the yield point earlier than usual.

2.3 Peel Stress

Due to the shift in neutral axis with a single sided repair, unwanted secondary bending moments are introduced. These bending moments create high peel forces at the ends of repair. Tapering the repair ends and increasing the overlap length takes care of this problem. Peel (through the thickness) stresses have been shown to increase with increase in patch thickness and decrease with increase in adhesive thickness. The maximum peel stresses induced in the adhesive and adjacent adhered (skin) at the end of the overlap is given by

$$\sigma_{\text{peel}} = \tau_{\text{max}} \left[\frac{3E_z(1-\nu_{zx}^2)t_r}{E_x t_A} \right]^{1/4} \quad (1)$$

where τ_{max} is the maximum shear stress in the adhesive, E_z is adhesive elastic modulus in the z direction, ν_{zx} is the Poisson ratio in the zx plane, t_r is the thickness of the repair patch, E_x is the adhesive elastic modulus in the x direction and t_A is the thickness of the adhesive.

2.4 Stress Intensity Factor

Reduction in the stress intensity factor (SIF) is the key issues in designing a patch. There is a considerable decrease of SIF just by applying one layer of patch. The rate of decrease of stress intensity is monotonic with the increase in the patch thickness. An increase in skin thickness causes an increase in the SIF; an increase of the fiber stresses near the crack and an increase of adhesive stresses near a crack, but has little effect in the adhesive stresses at the edges of patch. The damage tolerance and durability of repaired structure can be assessed by analyzing the SIF and crack growth rate and establishing a relationship between the two. The fatigue crack growth rate relationship (the Paris law) of un-patched panel is given

$$\frac{da}{dN} = C (\Delta K)^n \quad (2)$$

Where da/dN is the crack growth rate, a is the half crack length, N is the number of cycles, C and n are material constants, and ΔK is the stress intensity factor range.

3. DESIGN VARIABLES INPUT TO CRAS

Figure 1 shows our schematic diagram of the procedure for the design, modeling and analysis of adhesively bonded composite patch repairs of damaged aluminum panels using CRAS. Thick octagonal composite patch [5] was designed as shown in Figure 2a using CRAS v0.3 developed by the United States Air Force. Separate patches were designed for a single sided repair of 25.4 mm (1 in) diameter hole simulating corrosion grind out and 12.7 mm (0.5 in) crack on the periphery of the corrosion grind-out on 2024 T3 Clad aluminum panel of 6.324 mm (0.249 in) and 3.175 mm (0.125 in) skin thickness. The resulting patch dimensions for the crack and corrosion grind-out and the number of plies that satisfy the design criteria are given in Table 1 and Table 2 respectively. The patches were designed for uniaxial tensile stress of $\sigma_{yy} = 0.279$ GPa (40.5 ksi) (90% of the skin material yield stress Y) with 400,000 cycles of fatigue loading at a uniaxial tensile stress of $\sigma_{yy} = 0.093$ GPa (13.5 ksi) (30% of the skin material yield stress Y). The edges of the patch were tapered to reduce the peel stresses developed. Finally two different patches 11 plies for 0.125 in skin and 22 plies for 0.249 in skin with stiffness ratios of 1.58 and 1.56 were chosen for repair of corrosion grind out and crack. The CRAS software also allows for static check of the stresses in the aluminum skin at certain points that satisfies the criteria set in [6,7]. The purpose of this check is to ensure that high stress concentration at the edges of the patch does not have a detrimental effect on the aluminum skin

4. SUPERIMPOSITION OF PATCH

4.1. Patch Design for Corrosion Grind-out and Crack

Patch dimensions for the simulated corrosion grind-out at depth of 2.54 mm (0.1inch) and 5.08 mm (0.2 in) were designed for 3.175 mm (0.125 in) and 6.3246 mm (0.249 in) skin thickness respectively using CRAS. The patch dimensions for the corrosion grind-out are shown

in Figure 2a. Patches were designed separately for crack length of 12.7 mm (0.5 in) and corrosion grind out of 25.4 mm (1 in).

Figure 1: Schematic diagram of procedure for the design, modeling and analysis of adhesively bonded composite patch repairs of damage in Aluminum panels using CRAS.

4.2. Superimposition of Patch for Crack and Corrosion grind-out damage types

Using the principles of superimposition a single patch was developed to repair both crack and corrosion grind out. The criterion for superimposition of patch is based on the following parameters of half the width of patch designed for corrosion grind-out (W1) and crack (W2) and

the radius (R) of the corrosion grind-out. If the overlap width of the patch (W1-R) designed for corrosion grind-out is greater than half width of the patch (W2) designed for crack, then a single patch as shown in Figure 2(b) designed for corrosion grind-out will satisfy the crack and corrosion grind-out repair and patch redesign is not required, else patch has to be re-designed until the superimposition criterion is satisfied.

Figure 2: Schematic of Superimposition of patch indicating the Taper ratio and the dimensions

Table 1: Octagonal Patch dimensions for Crack

Taper Ratio	Skin Thickness (mm)	Crack Length (inches)	Patch Dimensions (inches)					No. of Plies that satisfy the DC	Stiffness Ratio
			A	B	C	D	Θ		
20:1	0.249	0.5	6.73	9.69	5.51	6.33	20	17-25	1.58
20:1	0.125	0.5	2.5	5.5	1.81	3.6	20	7-13	1.58

Table 2: Octagonal Patch Dimensions for Corrosion grind out

Taper Ratio	Skin Thickness (inches)	Radius of Hole (inches)	Depth of Hole (inches)	Patch Dimensions (inches)					No. of Plies satisfy DC	Stiffness Ratio
				A	B	C	D	θ		
20:1	0.249	0.5	0.20	7.75	10.2	6.40	6.5	20	19-22	1.56
20:1	0.125	0.5	0.10	3.7	6.34	2.82	3.92	20	7-11	1.58

For both Table 1 and Table 2 the patch was developed for a uni-axial tensile stress of 40.5 ksi (90% of yield stress for 2024 T3 Al) with 400,000 cycles ,DC- Design Criteria

5. MODELING AND ANALYSIS USING ABAQUS

2024 T3 clad aluminum panel, 5521 boron/epoxy composite patch and FM 73 adhesive were modeled using ABAQUS. Figure 1 show a schematic diagram of the design, modeling and analysis of the adhesively bonded thick composite patch repair of crack and corrosion grind-out on aluminum panel[6,7]. As the CRAS software does not support the modeling and analysis of dual damage (corrosion grind and crack together) ABAQUS software was used for modeling and analysis of the aluminum panel, composite patch and the adhesive. The stress distributions and displacements results were obtained from ABAQUS.

5.1. Geometry

2024 T3 clad aluminum sheets of 457.2 x 203.2 x 3.175 mm (18 x 8 x 0.125 in) and 508 x 254 x 6.35 mm (20 x 10 x 0.25 in) were modeled with a through crack of 12.7 mm (0.5 in) and corrosion grind-out (blind hole) of 25.4 mm (1 in) diameter on the aluminum panel. The basic repair configuration is an octagonal unidirectional boron/epoxy patch with dimensions shown in Table 2 and each composite ply of 0.127mm (0.005 in) thickness, and FM-73 adhesive of 0.1778mm (0.007 in) thickness were modeled in ABAQUS. The uni-directional orientation of patches fibers were specified in the direction of the application of load and perpendicular to the crack. Due to the symmetry of loading and lay up about the Y axis, symmetry was modeled along the length.

5.2. Finite Element Analysis using ABAQUS

The part instances of the panel and composite patch with properties shown on Table3 were created to facilitate the meshing, boundary condition and interaction operations. Hexahedral and tetrahedral mesh elements with global seed mesh size of 5.08 mm (0.2 in) and 4.826 mm (0.19 in) were used for meshing the panel and composite patch respectively. Half symmetry boundary conditions were applied for modeling the panel, adhesive, and the composite patch, and a load of -0.1395 GPa (-20.25 ksi) was applied on the other edge of patched panel. The composite patch and the panel were then assembled together by the operation of tie of ABAQUS. The job is then submitted for analysis. The stress distribution, strain and displacements on the panel, the patch and the adhesive as shown in Figure 4, Figure 5 and Figure 6 respectively were obtained as a result of finite element analysis.

Table 3: Properties of various materials

Material	E1 (GPa)	E2, E3 (GPa)	ν_{12}, ν_{13}	ν_{23}	G12, G13 (GPa)	G23 (GPa)
2024-T3 Clad Al	72.345		0.32			
Adhesive FM 73	194.98		0.32			
Boron/Epoxy	21979	25.421	0.168	0.035	7.234	4.933

Subscripts indicate the direction: 1-normal to crack (along the fiber), 2-along the crack (perpendicular to fiber direction), 3-through the thickness.

4 (a) Unpatched:0.125 inch skin thickness panel

4 (b) Patched:0.125 inch skin thickness_11ply

4(c) Un-patched:0.25 inch skin thickness panel

4(d) Patched: 0.25 inch skin thickness_22 ply

Figure 4 Maximum axial stress distribution in 2024 T3 Clad Aluminum Panel

5(a):11 plies patch

5(b): 22 plies patch

Figure 5 Stress distributions (Von Mises) in composite patch layer

6(a): 11 plies patch

6(b): 22 plies

Figure 6 Stress distributions (Von Mises) in adhesive layer

6. EXPERIMENTAL VERIFICATION

6.1 Machining 2024 T3 Clad Aluminum Panels and Templates

2024 T3 Clad aluminum panels were machined to dog-bone shapes on Cincinnati Milacron SABRE-750 CNC Vertical Machining Center. The aluminum panel was machined such that the grain direction was aligned along the loading axis. Corrosion grind out of 25.4 mm (1.0 in) diameter was machined at the center of the panel and through crack of 12.7 mm (0.5 in) on the periphery of the circular corrosion grind-out as shown in Figure 2a was machined by wire EDM. A small hole of 0.508 mm (0.02 in) was drilled first at the intersection of the crack and circular corrosion grind out for the EDM wire to go through.

In order to cut the composite material to desired shape, metal specimens called “Templates” are commonly used. CAD/CAM was used to design and obtain octagonal and elliptical templates for 11 plies and 22 plies of composite patch from aluminum panel of 1.6002 x 609.6 x 1219.2 mm (0.063 x 24 x 48 in) on Cincinnati SABRE 750 CNC machine.

6.2. Fabrication of Composite Patch

Composite patch is made from boron/epoxy 5521 prepreg (Textron Specialty Materials Inc) with unidirectional lay-up of $[0]_n$ (where n is the number of plies) with fibers oriented in the direction of loading. The patches were applied to the aluminum using FM 73 (Cytec Fiberite) adhesive and co-cured in vacuum bagging hot bonder at a temperature ramp up rate of 5 °F /min to 250°F and soaked at this temperature for 60 minutes, followed by ramping down to 80°F at rate of 4°F/min[8,9].

6.3. Experimental Setup and Experimental Results

Tensile tests were conducted on test specimens of 2024 T3 clad aluminum of 0.125 in skin thickness with 12.7 mm (0.5 in) crack and 25.4mm (1in) diameter corrosion grind-out. The tests were conducted on Instron 4486 tension testing machine which has a maximum capacity of 200170N (45000 lbf). The specimen was loaded at a rate of 2.54 mm/min (0.1 in/min). A unpatched damaged specimen (with crack and corrosion grind-out) and patched damaged specimen repaired with thick composite patch of 11plies were subjected to tensile loading. The load vs displacement curves are shown in the Figure 7 for the unpatched and patched specimens.

Figure 7: Comparison of Maximum loads for un-patched and patched specimen

7. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Finite element analyses were carried for un-patched aluminum panel with crack and corrosion grind-out, panels patched with 11plies and 22plies for skin thickness of 3.175mm (0.125 in) and 6.3246 mm (0.25 in) respectively. The two panel-patch–adhesive assemblies were separated into their constituent components and the stresses and displacements in each of these components were studied separately and the results are presented in the Table 4. From these results it is observed that the stresses at the crack and corrosion grind-out reduced due to the application of superimposed thick patch repair and was effective in arresting the corrosion and crack propagation. The results indicate that stress at the tip of crack and corrosion grind-out reduced with increase in the number of plies. It was also found that the area of maximum stress shifted from crack front (for damaged un-patched specimen) to the edge of the patches for the patched specimen. The damage of un-patched specimen failed at the load of 155,680 N (35,000 lbf) and displacement of 7.62 mm (0.3in), while the damaged patched test specimen reached the maximum press capacity of 200,170 N (45000 lbf) and displacement of 15.24 mm (0.6 in) without failure.

Table 4: Stress Results from ABAQUS analyses

Model		Max .Stress (GPa) [Ksi]	Displacement(mm) [in]
Un-patched 0.125" Panel	Skin	0.2945[42.76]	0.508[2.005e-2]
Un-patched 0.25" Panel	Skin	0.2935[42.60]	0.508[2.000e-2]
11-ply Composite Patched Panel For 0.125" skin	Skin	0.1860[27.00]	0.515[2.028e-2]
	Patch	0.2590[37.60]	0.0689[2.716e-3]
	Adhesive	0.0343[4.981]	0.0747[2.944e-3]
22-ply Composite Patched Panel For 0.25" skin	Skin	0.161[23.381]	0.606[2.386e-2]
	Patch	0.231[33.53]	0.10756[4.235e-3]
	Adhesive	0.0495[7.193]	0.1132[4.466e-3]

8. CONCLUSIONS

From the results the following conclusions are made.

1. Procedure for the design and analysis of adhesively bonded thick composite patch repair of dual damage cases of corrosion grind-out and crack on the periphery of corrosion grind-out using the principles of superimposition has been developed.
2. The experimental and the FEA results indicate that a single patch designed by the superimposition principles was efficient in arresting the crack and corrosion propagation.
3. The aluminum panel skin stress reduced significantly after repair with unidirectional thick boron/epoxy composite patch.
4. Maximum stresses were found at the crack front and edges of corrosion grind-out in the direction of tensile loading.
5. After the application of composite patch repair, the regions of maximum skin stress shifted from the edges of corrosion grind-out and crack front to the patch edges.
6. Tensile test results show that the patch extends the load carrying capacity. The damage of un-patched specimen failed at the load of 155,680 N (35,000 lbf) and displacement of 7.62 mm (0.3 in) while the damaged patched test reached the maximum press capacity of 200,170 N (45000 lbf) and displacement of 15.24 mm (0.6 in) without failure.

9. ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This research was partially supported by USA Air Force Research Laboratory through contract to the University of Missouri Rolla Center for Aerospace Manufacturing Technologies, Contract No.FA8650-04-704.

10. REFERENCES

1. Ruschau, J. J. and Coate, J. E., "The Effectiveness of an Adhesively Bonded composite Patch Repair as Applied to a Transport Aircraft Lower Wing Skin", Proceedings of 41st International SAMPE Symposium, March 24-28, 1996, pp 532-543.
2. Kumar, A. M. and Singh, R., "3D Finite Element Modeling of A Composite Patch Repair", Proceedings of NISA USERS conference, December 4-5, 1995, pp 2159-2166.
3. Brewer, J.C., "Improving The Damage of Bonded Structure via Adhesive Layer Barriers." Proceedings of FEA-NASA symposium on the continued airworthiness of Aircraft Structures, Atlanta, Georgia, August 28-30, 1997, pp 417-424.
4. Achenbach, J. D. "Detection and Characterization of Cracks and Corrosion in Aging Aircraft Structures-Part2." Fracture and strength of Solids, 1999, pp.1139-1148
5. Okafor, A.C., Singh, N., Enemuoh, U.E. and Rao, S.V. "Design, Analysis and Performance of Adhesively Bonded Composite Patch Repair of Cracked Aluminum Aircraft Panels" in print.
6. Schubbe, J.J. and Mall, S., "Modeling of Cracked Thick Metallic Structure with Bonded Composite Patch Repair Using Three-Layer Technique", Composite Structures, 1999, Vol.45, pp 185-193.
7. Duong, C.N., Hart Smith, L.J., Grip, R., Kubo, M., and Anderson, B., "CRAS Design and Analysis Software for Bonded Composite Repairs" Sixth Joint FAA/DoD/NASA Aging Aircraft Conference, CA, Sept 16-19, 2002
8. Chue, C.H., Chou, W.C, Liu, T.J.C., "The Effects of Size and Stacking of Composite laminated Patch on Bonded Repair for Cracked Hole", Applied Composite Materials, 1996, pp 355-367
9. Heimerdinger, B. Ratwani, M. M., Ratwani, N. M. "Influence of Composite Repair Patch Dimension on Crack Growth Life of Cracked Metallic Structures." Proceedings of 'The Third Joint Conference on Aging Aircraft', September 20-23, 1999.